

Information as a Conserved Quantity? Part 2

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In Part 1, we argued that entropy for the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB), Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) cases appears as an average of information $\ln(\text{probability})$, following the definition of information science. In the FD and BE cases, there are two probabilities driving the interactions. In particular, for the FD case, there is $p(e_1)$ which represents the probability to have a particle with e_1 in the first place, but there is also a $(1-p(e_3))$ probability for the interaction to be successful because an e_1 cannot change into an e_3 unless there is a free e_3 level. Thus, two probabilities are present and there are two average information terms in the “entropy”, i.e. $p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) + (1-p(e_i)) \ln(1-p(e_i))$ (FD case). Similar considerations apply to the BE case.

In Part 1, we argued that the mathematics of maximizing entropy subject to constraints representing conserved quantities is equivalent to treating average information as a conserved quantity. Just as $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ represents the total energy, we argue that the average information represents the total energy. We note, however, that $d \text{Information} = A \sum_i dp(e_i) + B \sum_i e_i dp(e_i) = 0$, so changes in information are linked to the conserved particle number and energy and this creates a restriction on the allowable distribution. The question then is: Why should information be conserved? In Part 1, we argued that information represents a minimum (entropy a maximum) and so one could not have fluctuations which on average changed this value.

Here we consider the idea of information in a slightly different way. We argued in a previous note that even in two body elastic collisions in Newtonian mechanics, one cannot know the exact e_i, e_j outcome pair for an e_1, e_2 incoming pair. We suggested that this lack of information implies that there is probability in the problem and enforces the condition that $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_i)p(e_j)$ if $e_1+e_2 = e_i+e_j$. In other words, there seems to be a specific amount of information (or lack of information) in collisions at an a priori level. Fluctuations, on average, cannot, it seems remove this amount information and so we argue that this is why information behaves like a conserved quantity. The next question then becomes: Why should $\ln(p(e_i))$ or $\ln(\text{probability})$ in general represent information. Reasons have been given in information science and we try to consider this issue here as well.

Conserved Information

Information science defines information as:

$$\ln(\text{probability}) \quad ((1))$$

This definition ensures that for $p_1 * p_2$:

$$\ln(p_1 * p_2) = \ln(p_1) + \ln(p_2) \quad ((2)), \text{ i.e. information is additive.}$$

If one has an ideal gas, then:

$$\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{total}}/N \quad ((2))$$

In other words, an average may be linked with a conserved quantity. Following information science and assuming that information is conserved in an ideal gas:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) = \text{total information}/N \quad ((3))$$

Physically, one may have fluctuations $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$, but these cannot change conserved quantities in the physical problem i.e

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \rightarrow \sum_i dp(e_i) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E/N \rightarrow \sum_i e_i dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{If information is conserved then:} \quad \sum_i d(p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))) = 0 \quad ((5))$$

To see that this is the case explicitly:

$$\sum_i dp(e_i) \ln(p(e_i) + dp(e_i)) = \sum_i (-e_i/T) dp(e_i) + \sum_i dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((6))$$

Mathematically, one may view maximization of entropy subject to constraints of conserved quantities as equivalent to conserved information. The question then becomes: Why would one expect information to be conserved a priori?

Conserved A Priori Information

In a previous note, we argued that even in deterministic Newtonian mechanics an elastic collision between e_1 and e_2 yields possible outcome pairs e_i, e_j such that $e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j$. The question is: Does one know which pair will be produced? We argue that in general this is not known. In other words, Newtonian mechanics may be combined with probability. In such a case, one might expect that:

$$p(e_i)p(e_j) = \text{constant for any } e_i, e_j \text{ pair such that } e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j \quad ((7))$$

This suggests that there is a certain a priori loss of information in a Newtonian system. Alternatively, one may argue that there is a certain amount of known information, even in a single collision. These ideas hold for a single e_1, e_2 collision and carry over to an ideal gas which has many such collisions. We argue that a priori, there is a fixed amount of information in an ideal gas. This total information cannot be changed, just like particle number and total energy cannot be changed under:

$$p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i) \quad \text{if one sums overall } i \quad ((8))$$

We suggest that one should expect that information is a conserved quantity in such a problem. The question then becomes: Why does one use $-1 * \sum \text{probability}(i) \ln(\text{probability}(i))$ to describe information?

Describing Information

Information science defines information as: $-\ln(\text{probability } i)$ ((9))

The \ln is introduced to ensure that information is additive, i.e.

$$\ln(p_1 p_2) = \ln(p_1) + \ln(p_2) \quad ((10))$$

One may ask, however, Why is $p(e_i)$ used as the argument of \ln ?

We suggest, as in Part 1, that one must examine a physical interaction, i.e. reaction balance. In the MB case:

$$p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_i)p(e_j) \text{ if } e_1+e_2 = e_i+e_j \quad ((11))$$

$p(e_i)$ appears as the probability driver which accounts for the amount of information present, i.e. the elimination of certain information due to ((11)).

In the FD and BE cases:

$$p(e_1) (1-p(e_3)) p(e_2) (1-p(e_4)) = p(e_3) (1-p(e_1)) p(e_4) (1-p(e_2)) \quad ((12))$$

Here $p(e_1)$ and $(1-p(e_3))$ appear as separate probability-like structures. $p(e_1)$ is the MB probability for a particle with e_1 to be present, but that does not guarantee a successful interaction. $p(e_1)$ is multiplied by $(1-p(e_3))$ for the FD case because if the e_3 level is occupied a reaction of $e_1 \rightarrow e_3$ cannot occur. Similarly, $(1-p(e_1))$ appears because e_3 cannot scatter into e_1 if it is occupied. Thus, there seem to be two probabilities linked to the variable e_1 , $p(e_i)$ and $(1-p(e_i))$. There should be two total information values linked with these and one approximates a total with an average, just as $\sum \text{over } i p(e_i) e_i = E_{\text{total}}/N$. Then:

$$p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) + (1-p(e_i)) \ln(1-p(e_i)) = \text{total FD information} \quad ((13))$$

A similar expression holds in the BE case.

Considering this information ((13)) to be conserved, one may take the differential with respect to $p(e_i)$ and expect the result to be 0. For this to be the case, one requires that:

$$\sum \text{over } i dp(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)/(1-p(e_i))) = 0 \quad \text{FD case} \quad ((14))$$

The constraint $\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$ is already used for $\sum_i dp(e_i) - \sum_i d(p(e_i))$ (i.e the second first derivative piece) and so one would assume that:

$$\ln(p(e_i)/(1-p(e_i))) = -e_i/T \quad ((15))$$

This then imposes an restriction on $p(e_i)$ which guarantees ((14))

Formal Expression of Conserved Information

We suggest that it seems reasonable to assume that total information is conserved and to consider that the extremization of entropy subject to constraints is really a statement of information being conserved. To see formally that information is conserved, we consider only the probability expressions ((7)) and ((13)) and ignore $e_1+e_2=e_i+e_j$ for the time being. Taking \ln of both sides yields:

$$\ln(p(e_1)) + \ln(p(e_2)) = \ln(p(e_i)) + \ln(p(e_j)) \quad ((15))$$

If $\ln(p(e_i))$ is called information, then information is a conserved quantity. For the FD and BE cases:

$$\ln(p(e_1)) - \ln(1-p(e_1)) + \ln(p(e_2)) - \ln(1-p(e_2)) = \ln(p(e_3)) - \ln(1-p(e_3)) + \ln(p(e_4)) - \ln(1-p(e_4)) \quad ((16))$$

In this case, one sees that minus signs appear. This follows because ((16)) is really an expression linked to conservation of energy. Thus, information terms are used to create the energy in question. To create the appropriate conserved information, one must consider information in the context of energy, i.e.

$$d \text{ information} = A \sum_i dp(e_i) + B \sum_i e_i dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((17))$$

In other words, $p(e_i)\ln(p(e_i))$ and $(1-p(e_i))\ln(1-p(e_i))$ pieces create the overall total information, but to obtain the sign between the two, one must have ((17)) apply. For the FD case, this leads to:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) + (1-p(e_i)) \ln(1-p(e_i)) \text{ as the appropriate total information term.}$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that probability appears in a single Newtonian elastic collision $e_1+e_2 \rightarrow e_i+e_j$. In particular, we suggest that any e_i, e_j pair can occur with the same product probability $p(e_i)p(e_j)$. Thus, even a single interaction has an intrinsic amount of information. In an ideal gas, there are many such interactions and so there should also be a fixed/conserved amount of information in the system, we argue. The question then becomes: How does one express information mathematically. We suggest that the key is to consider the reaction which is linked

with statistical properties. The qualitative information statement follows from $p(e_i) p(e_i) = p(e_1)p(e_2)$. Thus, $p(e_i)$ is the probabilistic driver of the statistical situation. Taking \ln of both sides shows that $\ln(p(e_i))$ behaves as a conserved quantity. It just so happens that $p(e_i) = -e_i/T$, with e_i being another conserved quantity. A similar result holds for the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, but there are two probability-like structures and one must try to determine the sign between the two.. We suggest that:

$d \text{ Information} = 0$ because information is conserved, but that:

$$d \text{ information} = A \sum_i dp(e_i) + B \sum_i e_i dp(e_i) = 0$$

because energy and particle number are also conserved and there is constraint between information and these. Thus, $d \text{ information}=0$ does not stand on its own. Rather, the above equation forces a certain distribution to arise. Nevertheless, information seems to be conserved, we argue. In the FD and BE cases, the above equation fixes the sign between $p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ and $(1-p(e_i)) \ln(1-p(e_i))$.